

Endogenous Vaults: Roles and functions in health and diseases

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Summary

Vaults are large ribonucleoprotein particles, with a molecular weight of 13 MDa, in the cytoplasm of many eukaryotic cells. They first reported in the mid-1980s. These particles consist of the Major Vault Protein (MVP), the Vault Poly- (ADP-Ribose) -Polymerase (VPARP), the Telomerase-associated Protein (TEP1) and small RNAs (vRNA). There are approximately 10.000 vault particle per cell. Their majority is detected in cytoplasm, where they can interact with cytoskeletal elements. A small amount of vaults is also found to be associated with the nucleus. Little are known about the biological role of vault particles. However, their structure and their cellular detection show that these complexes have a role in intracellular transport. Recent studies support that vaults have, also a role in Multi Drug Resistance (MDR). Some other functions have also attributed to these particles, such as participation in infection process, signal pathways, cell survival and DNA repairing. Recent studies have also demonstrated that vaults have the potential to serve as transporters. Vaults could be engineered and used as nanocapsules in order to carry vaccines, drugs or other molecules in target locations and activate immune responses. Finally, preliminary find-

ings in our laboratory, show that MVP is increased in patients with an inflammation of infectious etiology, indicating a role of vaults in infection process as it has already been supported in recent studies.

Key words

Vaults, MVP, infection, vaccine

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Introduction

Vaults are the largest ribonucleoprotein particles in the cytoplasm of many eukaryotic cells. They were described for first time in 1986.¹ They were named vaults, on the grounds that their structure resembled the vaulted ceilings in cathedrals (Figure 1). Their functions have not been fully elucidated although various studies suggest that they are involved in multidrug resistance.

Vaults: Structure & components

Vaults are barrel shaped particles with dimensions of approximately $41 \times 41 \times 72.5$ nm and a molecular weight of 13 MDa.² They are the largest known ribonucleoprotein particles in eukaryotic cells with an 8-2-2 symmetry. Their interior volume could be able to encompass several 70S ribosomes or hundreds of proteins and RNAs. Vault, in low PH, tend to splitting at the middle into two half vaults, resembling a flower – like structure. Each half consists of eight rectangular petals arrange around a central ring (Figure 2).³

Vaults are composed of three proteins; major vault protein (MVP) (96 kDa); vault poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase (VPARP) (193 kDa); telomerase-associated protein 1 (TEP1) (290 kDa); and small untranslated RNA (vRNA). Mammalian vaults contain 96 molecules of MVP, 8 molecules of VPARP, 2 molecules of TEP1 and at least 6 molecules of vRNA.³⁻⁶ MVP accounts for more than 70% of their mass (Figure 3). The monomers of MVP are able to interact via their coiled – coil domains at their C-terminal.⁷ It has been also demonstrated that MVP interacts with the tumor suppressor PTEN,

in a Ca^{2+} dependent manner.⁸ VPARP is a functional PARP family member that catalyzes the ADP-ribosylation of itself and MVP. This is the only demonstrated enzymatic activity of vaults complexes.⁶ The C-terminal of VPARP binds to the N-terminal of MVP.⁷ TEP1, a protein found to be associated with the telomerase complex, is necessary for RNA binding and stabilization of vault particles.^{9,10} This protein is able to bind to the telomerase RNA and to vRNA.^{4,9-11} On the other hand, vRNA comprises about 5% of the mass of vault. In humans, there have been detected three different genes of vRNA (hvg1 -hvg3) on chromosome 5, with a sequence conservation.¹² It has also been reported a fourth vRNA gene (hvg4) recently.¹³

Vaults: Highly conserved particles

Vaults are highly conserved particles which are present in a variety of eukaryotic organisms. Homologues of MVP and structures of similar dimension and morphology with vaults are present in numerous species from protozoa to metazoans. There have been identified vault – like structures in molluscs, the slime mold, *Dictyostelium discoideum*, echinoderms, fish, amphibians, avians and mammals.^{14,15} However, vaults have not been detected in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Caenorhabditis elegans*, *Drosophila melanogaster* and the plant *Arabidopsis sp.*¹⁶ Vault particles are though not to exist in prokaryotes. However, there are some proteins that have sequence similarities with MVP in these organisms, such as a colicin uptake transmembrane protein in cyanobacteria and a band 7 protein in *Her. Aurantiacus*.¹⁷

Figure 1

A) Transmission electron microscope (TEM) image of vaults (*ACS Nano. 2014; 8(11):11552-9*).
 B) Vaulted ceilings in cathedrals.

Figure 2

A) Schematic drawing, presenting the mechanism of vault opening into two halves and then in a flower - like structure, in low PH. B) Atomic force microscopy (AFM) image at pH 7.5, reclined full-vault (green arrowhead) and half-vaults (yellow arrowheads). AFM image at pH 6.0, upright full-vaults (blue arrowhead), reclining full-particle (green arrowhead) and flower-like structures (red arrowhead) (*Sci Rep.2016; 6:34143*).

Figure 3

The structure of vault particles and MVP monomer.

Figure 4 A) MVP detection on the nuclear envelope. Vesicular structures (enlarged in inset) appear MVP immunoreactivity (arrowheads) (*Cereb Cortex* 2009; 19 (7):1666–1677). B) The binding of vaults on microtubules (electron micrographs) (*Cell Motil Cytoskeleton* 2003; 56 (4):225–236).

Vaults: Intracellular localization

Vaults range from 10^4 to 10^7 particles per cell.¹⁸ The majority of these particles are detected in cytoplasm. Several groups have reported that they can interact with cytoskeletal elements such as microtubules (Figure 4).¹⁴ It has been demonstrated that vault movement over long distances is dependent on microtubules. A 5% of the vaults is found to be associated with the nucleus (nuclear membrane and nuclear pore complexes, NCP) (Figure 4). Recent studies have also indicated a role of these particles in NPC biogenesis.^{19–21}

Vaults: Biological role

Intracellular transport: Very little are known about the biological role of vault. Both the morphology and the intracellular localization of these particles led to the hypothesis that they could have a critical role in nucleo-cytoplasmic transport. Vaults are large enough to encapsulate proteins, RNAs, viruses, cellular organelles and transport them from the periphery to the nucleus and vice versa possible via microtubules.

Infection: Recent studies have notified that vault particles have a role in process of infection. The ex-

pression of MVP found to be enhanced during the infection from viruses such as hepatitis C virus (HCV), vesicular stomatitis virus (VSV), influenza A virus (IAV), and enterovirus 71 (EV71). It was demonstrated that MVP is virus induced and has the ability to up-regulates type-I interferon production, activate the immune response and reduce the viral replication.²² In case of hepatitis B virus (HBV), levels of MVP are also elevated, that leads to type-I IFN production, but HBV has developed mechanisms of immune evasion by disrupting and limiting type-I IFN antiviral activity.²³ Another study indicated that vtRNAs are upregulated in Epstein–Barr virus (EBV)-infected human B cells. An EBV protein (latent membrane protein 1, LMP1) provokes the up-regulation of vtRNA, which in turn inhibits both the extrinsic and intrinsic apoptotic pathways.²⁴

According to a recent study, MVP has also a role in the protection of *Listeria* from autophagy. *Listeria monocytogenes* is a bacterium induces listeriosis, a human infection with approximately 30% mortality.²⁵ As several intracellular microorganisms, *Listeria monocytogenes* is killed by autophagy, a mechanism of immune system that protects the hosts against infection.²⁶ More specifically, bacteria firstly undergo ubiquitination and then are degraded in autolysosomes by autophagy machinery.^{27,28} However, *Listeria* has developed mechanisms to escape from the immune sy-

stem and autophagy.^{29,30} *L. monocytogenes* produces the surface protein Internalin (InlK). It was indicated that InlK protein protects the bacteria against autophagy. Dortet et al reported that InlK is able to bind MVP. These interactions occur in the cytosol of infected cells. *Listeria* is capable to invest its surface with MVP, via InlK, in order to evade from autophagy. In this regard, the vast majority of MVP-masked bacteria are completely devoid of autophagy marker labeling, none of them are engulfed in an autophagosome and thus exhibit an increased survival rate (Figure 5).³¹

Signal pathways: Several studies have indicated that vaults and their components are important regulators of intracellular signaling.³³ MVP interacts with class A scavenger receptor (SR-A) leading to the p38/JNK mediated TNF- α production and apoptosis in macrophages.³⁴ In addition, MVP binds to the tumor-suppressor phosphatase PTEN, mediates its nuclear import and regulates its function.³⁵⁻³⁷ Moreover, MVP binds to constitutive Photomorphogenic 1 (COP1), an E3 ubiquitin ligase which is involved in the degradation of p53 and c-Jun.^{38,39} The interaction of MVP with COP1 is critical for the c - Jun degradation.⁴⁰

Cell survival and DNA repair: Vaults are demonstrated to regulate cellular proliferation and survi-

val.^{41,42} The genome of *Dictyostelium discoideum* encodes three different Mvps (MvpA, MvpB and MvpC). The disruption of two of the three MVP genes, under nutritional stress, induced growth and morphological defects.⁴² Vaults may also play a role in the DNA repair processes after ionizing radiation. MVP has linked to both DNA double strand breaks (DSB) machineries - homologous recombination (HR) and non-homologous end joining (NHEJ).⁴³

Cancer/MDR: A range variety of studies support that vaults play a role in multidrug resistance (MDR). In 1993, a protein which was named lung resistance-related (LRP), was overexpressed in a non-small-cell lung cancer cell line with doxorubicin resistance.⁴⁴ Two years later, in 1995, human MVP was identified to be the LRP. Except from MVP/ LRP, several other proteins have been linked to the phenomenon of MDR, such as p-Glycoprotein (an ABC-drug transporter), the human breast cancer resistance protein (BCRP) and members of the multidrug resistant protein family (ABCC1, ABCC2, ABCC3).⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷ MVP found to be expressed in 78% of 61 human cancer lines and its levels were associated with the resistance against drugs.^{48,49} Many clinico - pathological studies indicated that MVP expression at diagnosis was an independent adverse prognostic factor for response to chemotherapy.

Figure 5 Model for autophagy evasion by *L. monocytogenes*. *Listeria* is ubiquitinated by p62 and LC3. p62 is able to interact with ubiquitinated substrates and assist them to associate with the autophagosomal structural protein LC3.³² On the other hand, when MVP surface decoration is achieved via interaction with protein internalin (InlK), *Listeria* is protected from autophagy.

Based on the hypothetical transport function of vault particles, as well as on their cellular localization it has been supported that they have the potential to serve as transporters of drugs carrying them away from their subcellular targets. Vaults could be involved in multi-drug resistance by the extrusion from the nucleus and/or the sequestration of drugs into exocytotic vesicles. Vaults could also inhibit the entering of drug molecules in cell and/or in nucleus by isolating the drugs into their interior, blocking the entrance of drugs into the nucleus or directing them in the external cellular environment. In addition, vaults could operate as membrane transporters maybe in conjunction with intracellular membrane transporters and trigger drug efflux.

Support for the role of vaults in MDR, possibly by participating in the export of drugs, reported by Kumar et al. In their study, was indicated that vRNA interacts with chemotherapeutics. It was identified a mitoxantrone binding region within the vRNAs (hvg-1 and hvg-2) and it was also demonstrated that the interactions between the vRNAs and drug take place even in the cellular milieu (Figure 6). These evidences suggested that vRNAs are able to bind to chemotherapeutic compounds and that these interactions could play a critical role in the removal of drugs away from their intracellular targets.⁵⁰

Vaults: Innovative adjuvants and delivery vehicles for vaccines and drugs

Recent years vaults undergone modification, including encapsulation of selected molecules and cell – surface receptor targeting, in order to transfer a wide variety of molecules at target areas or cells.⁵¹⁻⁵⁶

The advantages of vaults in vaccine and drug delivery

Nowadays a range variety of drug delivery and targeting systems are being developed. Vaults are non - immunogenic particles which could be used as safe drug delivery vehicles. In contrast, protein assemblies like viruses, have reduced applicability on the grounds that they could be immunogenic.⁵⁷ In addition, vaults are dynamic structures with a large enough interior to encompass a variety of molecules, this fact led to the proposal that they could act as particles for the delivery of drugs, vaccines, proteins or nucleic acids.⁵⁸ On the inner side of vaults there are positively charged residues, which enable these particles to carry DNAs or RNAs, making them useful tools for gene therapy.⁵⁹ Moreover, as it has already notified above, vaults have the ability to open and close with PH changes. The possibility of separating vaults in a controllable man-

Figure 6 Secondary structure of vRNA-1 and possible binding positions of mitoxantrone (circles) (*Mol Cancer Res* 2010;8 (11):1536-1546).

ner could be a significant achievement. This would lead to an increased and controllable stability of vault particles, that would prolong the half – life of delivered drugs. It has also been demonstrated that HeLa cells can readily take up vaults from the culture media. Finally, a specific MVP targeting peptide, designated as minimal interaction domain (mINT) peptide of VPARP. mINT interacts also with heterologous proteins and direct them into vault particles. The delivered proteins are packaged and retain their properties.^{52,58}

Applications

The mINT peptide has already fused to membrane lytic domain of adenovirus protein VI (pVI) in order to improve the penetration of vault particles into target cells. These peptides were also used (in some cases complexed with antibodies) in order to target vaults to the receptor of epidermal factor (EGFR), which is up-regulated in a variety of cancer types (Figure 7).⁵¹

Moreover, the major outer membrane protein (MOMP) of *Chlamydia muridarum* was delivered in vault nanoparticles. These engineered particles were able to enhance the immune and provoke anti-chlamydia immune responses (Figure 8).⁵³

Figure 7 Schematic diagrams showing mINT peptide complexed with protein target (left) and a specific target peptide responsible for the binding of vault particles to cell receptor (right).

In addition, vault nano- capsules were engineered to deliver chemokine CCL21 to cancer cells.⁵⁵ Pre-clinical studies indicated that these particles induced immune system and attacked to cancer cells inhibiting their growth. Recently Rome and Buehler bioengineered a vault and thereby created an environment that allows bryostatin 1 to be loaded into the vaults. Vault could then realize bryostatin in cells infected from HIV and may could take part in the process of virus eradication. Further studies are being pursued in order to bring vault-loaded activators of latent HIV to clinical testing.

Figure 8 Modified vault packaged with the major outer membrane protein (MOMP) of *Chlamydia muridarum*.

Research approach: Vaults in inflammation of infectious etiology

In our laboratory we carried out a research study, in order to investigate the levels of MVP, in a large group of patients with inflammation. Our preliminary results, demonstrate that the levels of MVP are increased in sera of patients with an inflammation of infectious etiology. These results, in combination with recent studies which have associated the vaults and/or their components with infection (see above), indicate that these particles may have a critical role during the infection process. Taking these evidences together, it seems that vaults and/or their components have the potential to serve as biomarkers of infection.

Take – home - messages:

- Vaults are the largest ribonucleoprotein particles which have been discovered till now.
- Their functions still remain a mystery. They have certainly been associated with the phenomenon of Multi Drug Resistance in cancer.
- According to several studies and our preliminary results, they seem to play a role in infections.
- Recent studies, support that modified vaults could be used as promising novel vaccine or drug delivery vehicles.

Περίληψη

Ριβονουκλεοπρωτεϊνικά σωματίδια Vault : ο φυσιολογικός ρόλος και η λειτουργία τους

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Τα vaults είναι ογκώδη ριβονουκλεοπρωτεϊνικά σωματίδια, με μοριακό βάρος 13 MDa, που εντοπίζονται στο κυτταρόπλασμα πολλών ευκαρυωτικών κυττάρων. Ανακαλύφθηκαν για πρώτη φορά στα μέσα της δεκαετίας του 1980. Τα σωματίδια αυτά, αποτελούνται από την Major Vault Protein (MVP), την Vault Poly- (ADP-Ribose) -Polymerase (VPARP), την Telomerase-associated Protein (TEP1) και vault RNAs (vRNAs). Υπάρχουν περίπου 10.000 vault σωματίδια ανα κύτταρο. Τα vaults εντοπίζονται στο κυτταρόπλασμα, όπου συχνά συνδέονται και με στοιχεία του κυτταροσκελετού. Ένα μικρό ποσοστό τους, όμως, φαίνεται να συνδέεται και με τον πυρήνα. Ο βιολογικός τους ρόλος δεν έχει διευκρινιστεί πλήρως. Ωστόσο, η δομή τους και ο υποκυτταρικός εντοπισμός τους, δείχνουν ότι τα σωματίδια αυτά διαδραματίζουν κάποιο ρόλο στην ενδοκυτταρική μεταφορά. Έχει υποστηριχθεί, επίσης, ότι τα vaults έχουν κάποιο ρόλο στην αντίσταση που παρουσιάζουν οι ασθενείς με καρκίνο στην φαρμακευτική αγωγή. Στα vaults έχουν αποδοθεί και κάποιες άλλες λειτουργίες, όπως, είναι η συμμετοχή τους στην κυτταρική σηματοδότηση, στην κυτταρική επιβίωση και στην επιδιόρθωση του DNA. Ιδιαίτερο ενδιαφέρον παρουσιάζουν πρόσφατες μελέτες, σύμφωνα με τις οποίες τα vaults θα μπορούσαν να χρησιμοποιηθούν στην νανοβιοτεχνολογία. Έχουν γίνει προσπάθειες να δημιουργηθούν ανασυνδυασμένα vaults που θα χρησιμοποιηθούν ως μεταφορείς. Τα σωματίδια αυτά είναι ικανά να χρησιμοποιηθούν ως μεταφορείς εμβολίων, φαρμάκων και άλλων μορίων σε στοχευμένες περιοχές ενεργοποιώντας το ανοσολογικό σύστημα. Τέλος, πρωταρχικά αποτελέσματα από ερευνητική μελέτη στο εργαστήριό μας, δείχνουν ότι η MVP είναι αυξημένη σε ασθενείς με φλεγμονή λοιμώδους αιτιολογίας. Τα ευρήματα αυτά έρχονται να ενισχύσουν υπάρχουσες μελέτες σύμφωνα με τις οποίες τα vaults φαίνεται να διαδραματίζουν κάποιο ρόλο στις λοιμώξεις.

Bibliography

1. Kedersha NL, Rome LH. Isolation and characterization of a novel ribonucleoprotein particle: large structures contain a single species of small RNA. *J Cell Biol* 1986;103(3):699-709.
2. Mikyas Y, Makabi M, Raval-Fernandes S, Harrington L, Kickhoefer VA, Rome LH, et al. Cryoelectron microscopy imaging of recombinant and tissue derived vaults: localization of the MVP N termini and VPARP. *J Mol Biol* 2004;344(1):91-105.
3. Kedersha NL, Heuser JE, Chugani DC, Rome LH. Vaults. III. Vault ribonucleoprotein particles open into flower-like structures with octagonal symmetry. *J Cell Biol* 1991;112(2):225-35.
4. Kickhoefer VA, Stephen AG, Harrington L, Robinson MO, Rome LH. Vaults and telomerase share a common subunit, TEP1. *J Biol Chem* 1999; 274 (46): 32712-7.
5. Kong LB, Siva AC, Kickhoefer VA, Rome LH, Stewart PL. RNA location and modeling of a WD40 repeat domain within the vault. *RNA* 2000;6(6):890-900.
6. Kickhoefer VA, Siva AC, Kedersha NL, Inman EM, Ruland C, Streuli M, et al. The 193-kD vault protein, VPARP, is a novel poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase. *J Cell Biol* 1999;146(5):917-28.
7. van Zon A, Mossink MH, Schoester M, Scheffer GL, Scheper RJ, Sonneveld P, et al. Structural domains of vault proteins: a role for the coiled coil domain in vault assembly. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun* 2002; 291(3): 535-41.
8. Yu Z, Fotouhi-Ardakani N, Wu L, Maoui M, Wang S, Banville D, et al. PTEN associates with the vault particles in HeLa cells. *J Biol Chem* 2002;277(43):40247-52.
9. Kickhoefer VA, Liu Y, Kong LB, Snow BE, Stewart PL, Harrington L, et al. The Telomerase/vault-associated protein TEP1 is required for vault RNA stability and its association with the vault particle. *J Cell Biol* 2001;152(1):157-64.
10. Harrington L, McPhail T, Mar V, Zhou W, Oulton R, Bass MB, et al. A mammalian telomerase-associated protein. *Science* 1997;275(5302):973-7.
11. Poderycki MJ, Rome LH, Harrington L, Kickhoefer VA. The p80 homology region of TEP1 is sufficient for its association with the telomerase and vault RNAs, and the vault particle. *Nucleic Acids Res* 2005;33(3):893-902.
12. van Zon A, Mossink MH, Schoester M, Scheffer GL, Scheper RJ, Sonneveld P, et al. Multiple human vault RNAs. Expression and association with the vault complex. *J Biol Chem* 2001;276(40):37715-21.
13. Mrazek J, Kreutmayer SB, Grasser FA, Polacek N, Huttenhofer A. Subtractive hybridization identifies novel differentially expressed ncRNA species in EBV-infected human B cells. *Nucleic Acids Res* 2007; 35(10):e73.
14. Kedersha NL, Rome LH. Vaults: large cytoplasmic RNP's that associate with cytoskeletal elements. *Mol Biol Rep* 1990;14(2-3):121-2.
15. Rome L, Kedersha N, Chugani D. Unlocking vaults: organelles in search of a function. *Trends Cell Biol* 1991;1(2-3):47-50.
16. Kickhoefer VA, Vasu SK, Rome LH. Vaults are the answer, what is the question? *Trends Cell Biol* 1996; 6(5):174-8.
17. Daly TK, Sutherland-Smith AJ, Penny D. In silico resurrection of the major vault protein suggests it is ancestral in modern eukaryotes. *Genome Biol Evol* 2013;5(8):1567-83.
18. Kickhoefer VA, Rajavel KS, Scheffer GL, Dalton WS, Scheper RJ, Rome LH. Vaults are up-regulated in multidrug-resistant cancer cell lines. *J Biol Chem* 1998;273(15):8971-4.
19. Chugani DC, Rome LH, Kedersha NL. Evidence that vault ribonucleoprotein particles localize to the nuclear pore complex. *J Cell Sci* 1993;106 (Pt 1):23-9.
20. Hamill DR, Suprenant KA. Characterization of the sea urchin major vault protein: a possible role for vault ribonucleoprotein particles in nucleocytoplasmic transport. *Dev Biol* 1997;190(1):117-28.
21. Abbondanza C, Rossi V, Roscigno A, Gallo L, Belsito A, Piluso G, et al. Interaction of vault particles with estrogen receptor in the MCF-7 breast cancer cell. *J Cell Biol* 1998;141(6):1301-10.
22. Liu S, Hao Q, Peng N, Yue X, Wang Y, Chen Y, et al. Major vault protein: a virus-induced host factor against viral replication through the induction of type-I interferon. *Hepatology* 2012;56(1):57-66.
23. Liu S, Peng N, Xie J, Hao Q, Zhang M, Zhang Y, et al. Human hepatitis B virus surface and e antigens inhibit major vault protein signaling in interferon induction pathways. *J Hepatol* 2015;62(5):1015-23.
24. Amort M, Nachbauer B, Tuzlak S, Kieser A, Schepers A, Villunger A, et al. Expression of the vault RNA protects cells from undergoing apoptosis. *Nat Commun* 2015;6:7030.
25. Dortet L, Ploy MC, Poyart C, Raymond J, Ouet OR-PldF. Emergence of *Streptococcus pneumoniae* of serotype 19A in France: molecular capsular serotyping, antimicrobial susceptibilities, and epidemiology. *Diagn Microbiol Infect Dis* 2009;65(1):49-57.
26. Ogawa M, Yoshikawa Y, Mimuro H, Hain T, Chakraborty T, Sasakawa C. Autophagy targeting of *Listeria monocytogenes* and the bacterial countermeasure. *Autophagy* 2011;7(3):310-4.

27. Yoshikawa Y, Ogawa M, Hain T, Yoshida M, Fukumatsu M, Kim M, *et al.* Listeria monocytogenes ActA-mediated escape from autophagic recognition. *Nat Cell Biol* 2009;11(10):1233-40.
28. Thurston TL, Ryzhakov G, Bloor S, von Muhlinen N, Randow F. The TBK1 adaptor and autophagy receptor NDP52 restricts the proliferation of ubiquitin-coated bacteria. *Nat Immunol* 2009;10(11):1215-21.
29. Cossart P. Actin-based motility of pathogens: the Arp2/3 complex is a central player. *Cell Microbiol* 2000;2(3):195-205.
30. Kocks C, Gouin E, Tabouret M, Berche P, Ohayon H, Cossart P. L. monocytogenes-induced actin assembly requires the actA gene product, a surface protein. *Cell* 1992;68(3):521-31.
31. Dortet L, Mostowy S, Samba-Louaka A, Gouin E, Nahori MA, Wiemer EA, *et al.* Recruitment of the major vault protein by InlK: a Listeria monocytogenes strategy to avoid autophagy. *PLoS Pathog* 2011; 7(8): e1002168.
32. Pankiv S, Clausen TH, Lamark T, Brech A, Bruun JA, Outzen H, *et al.* p62/SQSTM1 binds directly to Atg8/LC3 to facilitate degradation of ubiquitinated protein aggregates by autophagy. *J Biol Chem* 2007; 282(33):24131-45.
33. Kramer AP, Kuwada JY. Formation of the receptive fields of leech mechanosensory neurons during embryonic development. *J Neurosci* 1983;3(12):2474-86.
34. Ben J, Zhang Y, Zhou R, Zhang H, Zhu X, Li X, *et al.* Major vault protein regulates class A scavenger receptor-mediated tumor necrosis factor- α synthesis and apoptosis in macrophages. *J Biol Chem* 2013; 288(27): 20076-84.
35. Minaguchi T, Waite KA, Eng C. Nuclear localization of PTEN is regulated by Ca²⁺ through a tyrosil phosphorylation-independent conformational modification in major vault protein. *Cancer Res* 2006; 66(24): 11677-82.
36. Chung JH, Ginn-Pease ME, Eng C. Phosphatase and tensin homologue deleted on chromosome 10 (PTEN) has nuclear localization signal-like sequences for nuclear import mediated by major vault protein. *Cancer Res* 2005;65(10):4108-16.
37. Chung JH, Eng C. Nuclear-cytoplasmic partitioning of phosphatase and tensin homologue deleted on chromosome 10 (PTEN) differentially regulates the cell cycle and apoptosis. *Cancer Res* 2005;65(18):8096-100.
38. Dornan D, Wertz I, Shimizu H, Arnott D, Frantz GD, Dowd P, *et al.* The ubiquitin ligase COP1 is a critical negative regulator of p53. *Nature* 2004;429(6987):86-92.
39. Wertz IE, O'Rourke KM, Zhang Z, Dornan D, Arnott D, Deshaies RJ, *et al.* Human De-etiolated-1 regulates c-Jun by assembling a CUL4A ubiquitin ligase. *Science* 2004;303(5662):1371-4.
40. Yi C, Li S, Chen X, Wiemer EA, Wang J, Wei N, *et al.* Major vault protein, in concert with constitutively photomorphogenic 1, negatively regulates c-Jun-mediated activator protein 1 transcription in mammalian cells. *Cancer Res* 2005;65(13):5835-40.
41. Vasu SK, Kedersha NL, Rome LH. cDNA cloning and disruption of the major vault protein alpha gene (mvpA) in Dictyostelium discoideum. *J Biol Chem* 1993;268(21):15356-60.
42. Vasu SK, Rome LH. Dictyostelium vaults: disruption of the major proteins reveals growth and morphological defects and uncovers a new associated protein. *J Biol Chem* 1995;270(28):16588-94.
43. Shimamoto Y, Sumizawa T, Haraguchi M, Gotanda T, Jueng HC, Furukawa T, *et al.* Direct activation of the human major vault protein gene by DNA-damaging agents. *Oncol Rep* 2006;15(3):645-52.
44. Scheper RJ, Broxterman HJ, Scheffer GL, Kaaijk P, Dalton WS, van Heijningen TH, *et al.* Overexpression of a M(r) 110,000 vesicular protein in non-P-glycoprotein-mediated multidrug resistance. *Cancer Res* 1993;53(7):1475-9.
45. Steiner E, Holzmann K, Elbling L, Micksche M, Berger W. Cellular functions of vaults and their involvement in multidrug resistance. *Curr Drug Targets* 2006;7(8):923-34.
46. Hall MD, Handley MD, Gottesman MM. Is resistance useless? Multidrug resistance and collateral sensitivity. *Trends Pharmacol Sci* 2009;30(10):546-56.
47. Scheffer GL, Schroeijers AB, Izquierdo MA, Wiemer EA, Scheper RJ. Lung resistance-related protein/major vault protein and vaults in multidrug-resistant cancer. *Curr Opin Oncol* 2000;12(6):550-6.
48. Izquierdo MA, Shoemaker RH, Flens MJ, Scheffer GL, Wu L, Prather TR, *et al.* Overlapping phenotypes of multidrug resistance among panels of human cancer-cell lines. *Int J Cancer* 1996;65(2):230-7.
49. Laurencot CM, Scheffer GL, Scheper RJ, Shoemaker RH. Increased LRP mRNA expression is associated with the MDR phenotype in intrinsically resistant human cancer cell lines. *Int J Cancer* 1997; 72(6):1021-6.
50. Gopinath SC, Wadhwa R, Kumar PK. Expression of noncoding vault RNA in human malignant cells and its importance in mitoxantrone resistance. *Mol Cancer Res* 2010;8(11):1536-46.
51. Kickhoefer VA, Han M, Raval-Fernandes S, Poderycki MJ, Moniz RJ, Vaccari D, *et al.* Targeting vault nanoparticles to specific cell surface receptors. *ACS Nano* 2009;3(1):27-36.
52. Goldsmith LE, Pupols M, Kickhoefer VA, Rome LH, Monbouquette HG. Utilization of a protein "shuttle" to load vault nanocapsules with gold probes and proteins. *ACS Nano* 2009;3(10):3175-83.
53. Champion CI, Kickhoefer VA, Liu G, Moniz RJ, Freed AS, Bergmann LL, *et al.* A vault nanoparticle

- vaccine induces protective mucosal immunity. *PLoS One* 2009;4(4):e5409.
54. Buehler DC, Toso DB, Kickhoefer VA, Zhou ZH, Rome LH. Vaults engineered for hydrophobic drug delivery. *Small* 2011;7(10):1432-9.
 55. Kar UK, Srivastava MK, Andersson A, Baratelli F, Huang M, Kickhoefer VA, *et al.* Novel CCL21-vault nanocapsule intratumoral delivery inhibits lung cancer growth. *PLoS One* 2011;6(5):e18758.
 56. Lai CY, Wiethoff CM, Kickhoefer VA, Rome LH, Nemerow GR. Vault nanoparticles containing an adenovirus-derived membrane lytic protein facilitate toxin and gene transfer. *ACS Nano* 2009;3(3):691-9.
 57. Mastrobattista E, van der Aa MA, Hennink WE, Crommelin DJ. Artificial viruses: a nanotechnological approach to gene delivery. *Nat Rev Drug Discov* 2006; 5(2):115-21.
 58. Kickhoefer VA, Garcia Y, Mikyas Y, Johansson E, Zhou JC, Raval-Fernandes S, *et al.* Engineering of vault nanocapsules with enzymatic and fluorescent properties. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 2005; 102(12): 4348-52.
 59. Querol-Audi J, Casanas A, Uson I, Luque D, Caston JR, Fita I, *et al.* The mechanism of vault opening from the high resolution structure of the N-terminal repeats of MVP. *EMBO J* 2009;28(21):3450-7.